

FAIR-IMPACT

Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC

FAIRCORE4EOSC

Project Titles	Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC & Core Components Supporting a FAIR EOSC
Project Acronyms	FAIR-IMPACT & FAIRCORE4EOSC
Grant Agreement No.	101057344 & 101057264
Start Date of Projects	2022-06-01
Duration of Projects	36 months
Project Websites	www.fair-impact.eu & www.faircore4eosc.eu

Kernel Metadata – Agreed Recommendations on Metadata for Persistent Identifiers

Lead Author (Org)	Josefine Nordling (CSC)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Wim Hugo (DANS), Sven Bingert (DWDG), Hervé I' Hours (UESSEX-UKDS), Parham Ramezani (LifeWatch ERIC), René van Horik (DANS), Martin Matthiesen (CSC), Lassi Lager (CSC), Renato Juacaba Neto (EMBL-EBI), Natascha van Lieshout (SURF)
Date	2025-03-28
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15096004

Disclaimer

FAIR-IMPACT has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe funding programme for research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101057344. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

FAIRCORE4EOSC

Project Number: 101057264

Start Date of Project: 01/06/2022

Duration: 36 months

Funded by the European Union

Kernel Metadata – Agreed Recommendations on Metadata for Persistent Identifiers

Joint FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC discussions

Kernel metadata is a concise, standardised set of terms created to support simple yet consistent object descriptions for efficient collection management. Its goal is to strike a balance between providing enough detail for meaningful use, allowing easy machine processing, and enabling straightforward human interaction with metadata records.¹

The following recommendations are based on collaborative discussions between partners of the FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC projects, as well as a selected few CSC colleagues.

Distinguishing Kernel Metadata and Custom Metadata

Metadata for Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) is categorised into Kernel Metadata and Custom Metadata, each serving distinct roles in resource identification and management:

1. Kernel Metadata

Kernel Metadata is managed by the formalised system overseeing the PID Stack. It is typically standardised or based on well-documented schemas, although exceptions exist. It consists of two primary components:

- a. Identifier Metadata: Includes details about the identifier's creation, modification history, and associated redirection URLs. This metadata is maintained by the resolution service, which may operate within a federated or chained system.
- b. Resource Metadata: Commonly standardised and provided by the Provider. This metadata describes key aspects, such as citation details, subject classification, licensing, and rights management. Importantly, it usually reflects only the latest version of the resource, and not all PID systems follow a standardised schema for this metadata.

FAIR Digital Objects aim to extend Kernel Metadata to enhance resolution capabilities and machine-actionability. Alternative approaches, such as ARK inflections or Signposting, also support similar objectives.

2. Custom Metadata

Custom Metadata is the metadata presented on a resource's landing page or the most common resolution target. It is typically managed by the resource Owner or Manager and serves as the authoritative metadata version. Unlike Kernel Metadata, it is often aligned with domain-specific or format-specific standards, offering greater flexibility and detail.

Custom Metadata may also:

- Extend Kernel Metadata or map to it.
- Preserve older metadata versions and provenance records.
- Provide detailed contextual information tailored to specific research or application needs.

¹ <https://www.dublincore.org/groups/kernel/spec/>

By distinguishing Kernel and Custom Metadata, researchers and service providers can ensure consistency, persistence, and discoverability in metadata management while accommodating domain-specific requirements.²

There are two perspectives on managing Custom Metadata. One approach views Custom Metadata as the authoritative version, maintained in a decentralised manner by Owners and Managers. The other, as seen in initiatives like FDO, positions Custom Metadata higher in the resolution chain by incorporating it into Kernel Metadata. Both approaches have their advantages and drawbacks, which Hugo, W. et al. (2024) outline in their report.³

Recommendation - What?	Stakeholder affected - For whom?	Problem statement - Why?
Including sensitive metadata in the kernel metadata is to be discouraged.	Applies to the PID Manager and not to the PID Service Provider. The Provider should never be responsible for this.	Having no sensitive data in the kernel removes the need for authentication and permissions for kernel metadata. Additional layers (separate file) of non-kernel metadata can be deployed if necessary.
Include the notion of “open” or “closed” in the kernel metadata.	PID Service Provider to enact/enable PID User to define	Kernel metadata assists in efficient management of huge amounts of records with its machine-readable metadata. Defining whether open or closed is a crucial piece of information for identifying the terms of use and conditions for querying data.

² Hugo, W., Van de Sompel, H., & Hakala, J. (2025). The PID Landscape - a Technical View (0.7 Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14881287> Direct link to content: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1eEzm4jBoJqkP4UPncn5Fv5FXB_Bi8p5ubgWTScWT-5A/edit?pli=1&tab=t.0#bookmark=id.x0fw9ukjz84h

³ Hugo, W., Van de Sompel, H., & Hakala, J. (2025). The PID Landscape - a Technical View (0.7 Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14881287> Direct link to content: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1eEzm4jBoJqkP4UPncn5Fv5FXB_Bi8p5ubgWTScWT-5A/edit?pli=1&tab=t.0

Having kernel information in place enables findability when querying across a graph (e.g. scientific knowledge graph or PID graph)	PID Service Provider	Lack of kernel information as an additional layer makes it difficult to navigate selected information within a graph.
An agreed subset of required minimum metadata commonly and consistently expressed across PID service providers is the ideal, should the PID service provider support a standardised / common approach towards metadata representation.	PID Service Provider	Harmonisation across PID service providers would allow interoperability across the systems.
Kernel metadata to include administrative identifier metadata (e.g., when created what it points to) streamlined across PID service providers.	PID Service Provider to enact/enable PID User to describe	Harmonisation across PID service providers would allow interoperability across the systems. Administrative metadata improves PID monitoring capabilities.
Kernel metadata is especially important for describing physical objects e.g., instruments or samples.	PID Service Provider to enact/enable PID User to describe	Ensures entities are found in a reliable and consistent manner.
The kernel metadata should be closely coupled to the PID itself.	PID Service Provider	This caters for machine-actionability.
Information, such as author name, should not be included in the kernel.	PID Service Provider	The information going into the kernel is to be kept at a minimum and should serve to support machine-actionability.

Use the PID Meta Resolver ⁴ service to help decide what type of information goes under the authoritative metadata.	PID User	It can be difficult for the individual to figure out what kind of metadata from each item to resolve. This is best managed through machine-actionability.
Kernel metadata requires long-term maintenance. It is preferable to allow solutions where this is easier for the Manager to perform.	PID Manager	Maintenance of kernel metadata is crucial in cases where the underlying information changes and which affects the correctness of the kernel.
Kernel metadata is preferably quite flexible, including data related to administrative identifier, registration, and the original target (how long it's been available for resolution and whether it has changed).	PID Service Provider	Maintenance of kernel metadata is crucial in cases where underlying information changes and which affect the correctness of the kernel.
If not resolving, the kernel metadata could contain which version was the last version to resolve, so that this version could be retrieved from the Internet Archive.	PID Service Provider	Maintenance of kernel metadata is crucial in cases where the PID does not resolve.
There is a limited version control system for Handles, but it provides information making it possible to go back in time (time stamp), i.e. you can query the PID log to get to the last resolvable version, and the Handle system makes use of key value pairs for identification purposes.	(Handle) PID Service Provider	Ensuring the correctness of the referenced objects and for provenance assurance purposes.

⁴ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/eosc-pid-meta-resolver-pidmr> (not yet available on March 28th, 2025)